

Emotional Intelligence: The Relationship between Self-Regard and Communication Effectiveness

Hassan Jorfi, Saeid Jorfi, Hashim Fauzy Bin Yaccob, Ishak Mad Shah

Abstract—In today's complex global environment, emotional intelligence in educational administrations encompasses self-regard that is formed to utilize communication effectiveness. The paper is undertaken to understand the relationship between managers' emotional intelligence especially self-regard and employees to improve communication effectiveness in educational administrations of Iran. Data ($N = 145$) for this study were collected through questionnaires that participants were managers and employees educational administrations of Iran. The aim of this paper assess the emotional intelligence especially self-regard of managers and employees and its relationship with communication effectiveness in educational administrations of Iran. This paper explained self-regard that has a high relationship with communication especially communication effectiveness. Self-regard plays an important role in communication effectiveness. Individuals with high self-regard tend to have higher emotional intelligence and this action lead to improve communication effectiveness. The result of the paper shows a strong correspondence between self-regard and communication effectiveness in educational administrations.

Keywords—Emotional Intelligence, Self-Regard, Communication Effectiveness, Motivation.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE literature indicates recent applications of emotional intelligence especially self-regard and how they can improve communication effectiveness. This manuscript describes emotional intelligence of managers and employees of educational administration have a direct role to improve communication effectiveness. According to Goleman et al the definition of emotional intelligence is the ability to handle manners so that they are expressed effectively, enabling individual to work together smoothly against their general [13].

Hassan Jorfi. Management and Human Resource Development Faculty. University Technology Malaysia (UTM). Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia (0060176125344, 00989163007040, fax: 0612222-4300. E-mail: haassan_jorfee@yahoo.com, Hassan.jorfi@yahoo.com).

Saeid Jorfi, Management Faculty. University Technology Malaysia (UTM). Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. (E-mail: said_jorfi@yahoo.com).

Hashim Fauzy Bin Yaccob. Head of Department of Human Resource Development. University Technology Malaysia (UTM). Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia (E-mail: hfauzy@utm.my).

Ishak Mad Shah. Department of Human Resource Development. University Technology Malaysia (UTM). Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia (e-mail: ishak@utm.my).

Self-regard plays an important role in emotional intelligence. Self-regard is individuals' perception of themselves. The self concept can be an agent and motivates individuals to take on an action. Those people who see themselves positively tend to engage in communicating with others and doing a better work in connecting with others. A study showed that self-regard is positively correlated with emotional intelligence [34]. In other words, individuals with high self-regard tend to have higher emotional intelligence and this action lead to improve communication effectiveness. The goal of introducing instruction emotional intelligence with communication effectiveness was to expose managers and employees to a framework that describes specific competencies needed for educational administration. People with high self-regard are likely to have good communication, and will probably be successful in anything they decide to do. On the other hand, people with low self regard are likely to have a hard time in communication with others.

II. EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

Matthews defined emotional intelligence as individuals' way that leads to experience emotions and it can manage their emotions while communicating with others [21]. Researchers as Goleman and Matthews assert that emotional intelligence plays an important role to perception how person carries himself and connects with others [12, 21]. Also Matthews expressed that individual's emotional intelligence level reflects the value of communication with others [21]. The term of emotional intelligence appeared by Daniel Goleman, a science writer for the *New York Times* and a Harvard trained psychologist in the beginning of twenty century and became famous during the 1990's. Daniel Goleman developed the term of emotional intelligence in his book in 1995's. The book was under the title: *Why It Can Matter More Than IQ for Character, Health and Lifelong Achievement*. Dulewicz and Higgs and Langley (2000) believe that emotional intelligence plays key role in psychology and it has direct relating with communication effectiveness for develop the organizations [35, 36]. Cherniss and Dries & Pepermans argue that emotional intelligence improved organizational performance that is relating with career development strategies in the

workplace [37, 38]. Diggins, Goleman, Mayer & Salovey; and Rosete and Ciarrochi show that intellectual quotient is necessary for communication effectiveness but not sufficient [12, 22, 24, 26, 39]. Despite the vital role that emotional intelligence could play key role in communication effectiveness as well as career prospects in organizations, managers, employees and executives. They want to understand the term of emotional intelligence, self regard and relationship with communication effectiveness. This paper tries to answer these questions by describing a model of EI. Though the model would require more research in future to add empirical strength, the aim of this paper is to help managers, executives, employees and other career aspirants' understand relationship between emotional intelligence and communication effectiveness in educational administrations.

III. SELF-REGARD

The concept of self-regard is individual's view of themselves. In brief it is how individual estimate themselves. According to Paradise and Kernis Self-regard divided into three categories: (a) high (positive), (b) low (negative) and (c) middle (neutral) [40]. The means of having high self-regard is that an individual has a high idea of oneself. Individuals with low self-regard observe themselves as not important and lower. They always tend to be negative. Sternberg and Vroom explained that in a successful interpersonal connection, every person has a positive self-regard [41]. They significance themselves and identify that they have something essential to supply to the interpersonal connection. In compare, those who have a low self-regard observe everything to their sense of self. Consequently, these persons are highly reflexive to the events. Kernis, Golman, Paradise, Wheatman, & Whitaker argued that, these individual, it may appear that their self-regard is always is "on the line" and requires to be secured against apparent threats. As time development for these individual is hard and difficult to progress a sense of self that is obviously defined and steady [42]. Gecas and Gecas & Schwalbe suggest that the term of self-regard consist of two dimensions: self-efficacy and self-worth [43, 44]. Degree that individuals see themselves as effective and adequate is called efficacy dimension and degree that individual felt they are an individual of worth and value is called worth dimension. According to Rosenberg there are several ways for accomplished enhancement of self-regard. (a) When self-regard has been lowered, individual might act in ways that develops their self-regard. They might make a feeling of themselves that is high positive by redefine the condition of work. This state helps the people to obtain self-regard (b) Self-verification is another way to increase self-regard [45]. Swann express that it is probable that individual look for increase their self-regard by participating themselves with people that study or confirm their identity [46]. Individual are more probable to keep interpersonal relationships where they are to confirm their personalities. (c) Constant challenge is another way to increase self-regard. Ability to create and maintain a positive vision about oneself is called constant

challenge. This constant challenge is show on a daily base. Caldwell, Lefforge, Silver and Silverman asserted that motherly emotional support was negatively connection with criminal behavior and positively connection with emotional happiness and comfort [47]. Cohn & Kao and Patterson, Snyder & Patterson indicates that positive known processes can keep a teenager from engaging in discordant behaviors [48, 49]. Other researchers have recommended that the emotional support received from parents can serve as a barrier in periods of pressure. Individual in one way or the other ways influence their self-regard through positive and negative events. Abend, Berry, Herlocker, Kernis, McNamara and Waschull discovered the area to which the level and stability of self-regard forecasted the influence that daily positive and negative events have on peoples' manners about themselves [50]. Negative and positive events had a direct effect on peoples who had an unstable self-regard. In compare, individual with a high self-regard rated positive events more favor and significant than individual with low self-regard.

IV. COMMUNICATION

The formal definition of communication displayed in the Webster's Dictionary is as follows: "the act of transmitting ideas through writing or speech; the means to transmit messages between places or persons." [28]. We give and receive messages by a process called communication. These messages impact our own behavior and self concept, and also the behavior and self concept of others. The way we communicate with others is important because that's how we let people know who we are, what we believe in, what our values are, and how we feel. Hackman and Johnson define communication as "the transfer of symbol [16]. This transfer allows for the creation of meaning within individuals". Symbols are anything that stands for, or represents, other things. Symbols are abstract, ambiguous, and arbitrary. Symbols have no natural or intrinsic relation to what they represent and they do not necessarily share the same meaning across individuals. Thus, the definition of communication used in this study posits that communication is an interactive and interdependent systemic process whereby meaning is generated using symbols in the form of verbal, written, nonverbal, and met communications. Luftman belief communication is the base of all human activities and relations with others [19]. Asimov expressed that communication has been an important factor in our evolution into civilized societies [2]. Communication plays an important and essential role in our personal and professional lives. Schermerhorn, Hunt & Osborn illustrated that at an organizational level, communication is essential in enabling an organization to complete its goals, vision and mission [25]. The success of an organization may lie in the ability of the manager to effectively communicate to the employees in educational setting.

V. COMMUNICATION EFFECTIVENESS

Communication is the process contained with the exchange of any kind of information or data .Communication effectiveness is a success factor for managers and employees . Effective communication does not happen automatically . Communication is an art and a science whereby techniques must be learned; which for some managers, the techniques of communication may come naturally .Effective manager communication can help employees acquire skills, raise their self-image, and also assist practitioners in earning employee respect. Thamhain argued that effective communication can add value to organizations [27]. Hersey et al suggests that there is a direct correlation between communication and effectiveness in some organizations [18]. Helgeson belief that junction of events has happened that requests modify in the meaning of effective communication [17]. These events need communication effectiveness such as increased diversity in the workers and the globalization of the emporium .In other words, commerce organization itself and the universe in which it competes have changed, in this state definition of effective communication is culminating in a change .Hersey et al defined communication effectiveness as person who delivers an obvious message, listens carefully, and receives and sends feedback [18]. Fisher and Wood express that communication effectiveness has the flexibility to scruple among stereotypical man or woman communication behavior as need for the condition [10, 29]. Gudykunst expresses that high level of communication effectiveness leads to a high degree of equalities of perceptions between the sender and the receiver [15]. In this perception, Kuncoro states that communication effectiveness of the manager's correlates positively with maximizing understanding or minimizing misunderstanding of employees [51]. Research by Chen illustrates that effective communication takes into account interact ants' gender, religion, and ethnicity when determining "the ability to negotiate cultural meanings and to execute appropriately effective communication behaviors" [6]. Fisher argues that effective communication is important in the place of work, in interactions, and in daily life [10]. Thamhain illustrates that effective communication can connect the employees, strengthen shared ideas, and develop teamwork and decision making in the organizations [27]. Even though effective communication is essential in individual relations and it can be hard to attain in the work .Communication mechanisms improve the manager's knowledge and understanding of communication effectiveness .The manager had to effectively convey individual's message in order to understand how and when to integrate into individual's communication style . Otherwise, the organization may redound to miscommunication, frustration, employee turnover, lack of communication, insufficient communication or ineffective communication causing disorder, and failure to achieve goals in organizations .In search toward power communication, Marshak recommends that the Communicator must apply certain elements to create greater effect on communication intellects such as active listening [20]. Active listening

integrates the circle of effective communication by focusing on how the message is sent and reply and feedback given to the communicator and individual's openness to that feedback. This paper explored the concept of emotional intelligence especially self-regard and communication effectiveness. Communication can be given in verbal, nonverbal, and written forms .Teaching required skills; presenting clear rules, policies, and strategies; developing consequences; and using nonverbal techniques, such as a simple smile to acknowledge employee performance, are examples of positive communication techniques .Providing positive and helpful feedback is vital to employee development and performance.

VI. SELF-REGARD AND COMMUNICATION EFFECTIVENESS

Self-regard is the way individuals think about themselves . Low self-regard for both men and women has been recognized as one of the most important prospects of violent relationships . Learning how to make self-regard and improving interpersonal skills is one way to avoid negative or violent relationships in the all aspects of life .People by learning better communication skills and achieving personal goals that make them feel good about themselves can improve their self-regard .People with high self-regard are probable to have good communication, and will likely be successful in everything they decide to do .On the other hand, people with low self-regard are likely to have a hard time in communication with others.By seeing individual with high self esteem, we can observe how they communicate effectively with others, how they confront negative reply, the way they talk, sit, walk, how they do their work or study and so on .We can learn from these people but we mustn't be like them we will lose our own solidarity .If we lose our own solidarity, it can devastate our self esteem.This paper strongly supports a positive relationship between communication effectiveness and emotional intelligence especially self-regard [3, 4, 9, 11, 23, 26]). Self-regard is inherently linked to communication .Self-regard is linked to thoughts, feelings, and behaviors that combine together in the process of interpersonal relations and the means by which interpersonal relations happen is communication.In summary, a communication view of self-regard on the interaction and relationship components of the process .The vision holds that self-regard is outcomes of the communicative process .It follows that to improve manager effectiveness requires a significant emphasis on communication effectiveness since according to this vision; it is through communication effectiveness that self-regard happen.

Fig.1 Communication effectiveness View of managers and Self-Regard

VII. MOTIVATION

Arkes and Garske defined the concept of motivation as those processes that influence the provocation, strength or direction of behavior or also Woolfolk defined motivation as an internal state that maintain behavior and arouses directs [53, 30]. Motivation consists of two types: (a) *intrinsic motivation*, and (b) *extrinsic motivation*. Intrinsic motivation means motivation that root from factors that do not want motives or punishments such as interest or pry because the motion itself is rewarding. Extrinsic motivation means motivation that rises from what individual will achieve. Individual do something in order to learn a reward, elude punishment, which is not associated to the task.

Johnson and Johnson proposed that for learning motivation there are many factors. These factors include :planning, compression on the goal, cognitive awareness of what people want to learn and how people want to learn it, the active explore for new information, clear understanding of feedback, pride and satisfaction in attainment [54].

VIII. MOTIVATION AND SELF-REGARD

Goleman and Lanser propose that motivation is an important factor of emotional intelligence especially self-regard that allow individual to understand and recognize this factor through the positive and negative aspects of working life by showing invention, assiduity and sacrifice, as well as being goal orientated, focused and proactive [14, 33]. In general self-regard of emotional intelligence plays a key role in organizations and increase motivation [52]. Abraham underscores the importance of motivation in relation to emotional intelligence especially self-regard in the following excerpt :“Emotional intelligence incorporates the quality of emotional resilience, or flexible optimism, which gives the individuals the ability to cope with interpersonal conflict Instead of engaging in the disruptive activity of faultfinding, emotionally intelligent employees are flexibly optimistic enough to put difficulties behind them and redirect their attention to conflict resolution, and they espouse a durable sense that they will succeed, despite setbacks and frustrations,” [1]. Dijk and Freedman indicated the there is relationship between self-regard and motivation. They argued, “People who require external reinforcement to be motivated are always at the mercy of others’ approval or reward system” [7]. The improvement of peoples’ self-regard will make them to feel better and safety; people will have trust in their powers, skills and abilities and we will see the others as equals to

people, not as superiors to them. The development of motivation will develop life, but also, at the same time, develop self esteem and this state leads to improve the self-regard.

Individual can improve their self esteem to feel better with them; with a high level of self-regard, motivation for the work will be improved because people will want to show the others the good they are in their job. Also, enhancing motivation for job produces as side effect the improvement of self esteem. As you see, both skills are interrelated, and usually the lack of motivation in a person will show occult low self-regard. Self hypnosis is the way to improve motivation for life and self-regard; in other terms, the hypnosis applied over your own to modify your inner patterns of thought saving new patterns of motivation, success, happiness and self-regard.

IX. MOTIVATION AND COMMUNICATION EFFECTIVENESS

Scott indicates that without a sufficient level of motivation, the communication may not be successful [32]. Anthony and Govindarajan show that an organization for improve decisions and financial success must increase motivation through development the communication [31]. Also, Edmondson argued that communication positively impact on employee motivations to speak up to their superiors about problems that happened while using a new work system [8]. Gibson and state good communications lead to high motivation for managers and employees of organization [55]. In general, the researcher achieve this result from written says, that motivation and communication are inseparable factors in daily life and work.

X. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The model for this paper is composed of four key constructs (see Figure2) including emotional intelligence, communications effectiveness, motivation, and self-regard. Based on the existing literature-as stated earlier- there is a positive relationship between emotional intelligence especially self-regard and communication effectiveness with motivation serving as a moderator of this relationship.

Fig. 2 Conceptual Framework

From the model, the following hypothesis is derived:

H1: Self-regard will have a significant relationship with communications effectiveness in educational administrations of Iran.

H2: Motivation will moderate a relationship between self-regard and communications effectiveness in educational administrations of Iran.

XI. EDUCATION ADMINISTRATION

The administration of higher education is connected by law and policy to the Iranian government by the concept of *velayat-i-faqih*, but the tight control over educational administration is a reflection of the power that student movements have traditionally had in Iranian politics. To a large degree, the revolution itself was a student movement, and, especially in the 1990s, unrest and protest against restrictive government policies were centered on university campuses. So the strong connection between the university system and the government has been a political necessity. Any decisions made at the institutional level must be approved by either The Ministry of Culture and Higher Education and its Supreme Council on Higher Education Planning or the Ministry of Health, Treatment, and Medical Education, depending on the nature of the institution. Decisions regarding the policies of higher education are made by these organizations under the approval of the Islamic Parliament, the Cabinet, and the Higher Council of Cultural Revolution. University administration is undertaken by the Board of Trustees, affirmed and appointed by the Higher Council of Cultural Revolution. By law, these trustees set university budgets, research finances, and teaching salaries, subject to the approval of the council. They are also responsible for supervision of the effective administration of educational research, cultural affairs, student, official, financial, construction, and discipline affairs, scientific services, all national and international relationships of the university or institution, and the coordinating and leading of different units and departments. The Educational Council forms the second institutional level of university administration. This council is made up of members of the administrative body and the deans of faculties, junior colleges, and research departments, as well as faculty teachers who are members of each institution's specialty council. Some of the duties of this council include the study and approval of short-term educational and research projects and new educational courses or fields.

XII. GOALS AND METHODS

The goal of the research was to determine the impact of emotional intelligence (self-regard) through motivation on communication effectiveness. The research was based on a questionnaire study, which is a quite common form of investigation in this behavior and business field and also

provides opportunities for determining whether emotional intelligence (self-regard) and motivation have an impact on communications effectiveness. The respondents for the research were selected from the Educational Administrations of Iran. The group comprised (82) persons, out of which (502) respondents completed the questionnaire.

To assess the relationship between self-regard and communication effectiveness, we used a three-part questionnaire. First part was BarOn EQ-i, which includes 133 questions in 5 categories and 15 scales. The five categories are Intrapersonal (Self-Regard, Emotional Self-Awareness, Assertiveness, Independence, and Self-Actualization), Interpersonal (Empathy, Social Responsibility, and Interpersonal Relationship), Stress Management (Stress Tolerance and Impulse Control), Adaptability (Reality Testing, Flexibility, and Problem Solving), and General Mood Scale (Optimism and Happiness). Second part was Communication Effectiveness Questionnaire which was completed by managers and employees in educational administrations. Third part was Motivation Questionnaire which was completed by managers and employees in educational administrations. The questionnaires were multiple-response questionnaire that response is measured on 5-point Likert-type scales and range from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree." The total score was the sum of all 14 scales scores. The minimum and maximum scores for each scale were 6 and 30 respectively and the maximum and minimum total score was 90 and 450 respectively [5]. These questionnaires were standardized to be used in Iran; its content validity was reported to be acceptable and its reliability was 0.93 by Cronbach's alpha. The Questionnaires were distributed among managers and employees in their administration or office environments and after explaining the aims and methodology of the study, they were asked to take the questionnaire home and return them back after completing. They had the option to complete the questionnaire or not and they were assured of the privacy of their personal data. Data were analyzed using SPSS-13. For each manager and employee, the total score of self-regard and the score of each scale were calculated. To analyze data, descriptive statistics (frequency, mean scores and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (independent t-test, ANOVA and Pearson correlation coefficient) were used.

XIII. RESULTS

All 145 managers and employees in educational administrations of Iran completed the emotional intelligence, communication effectiveness, and motivation questionnaires. The mean age of managers and employees were 21.03 ± 2.17 . 106 managers and employees (73.6%) were male and 90 (62.5%) were female. Table 1 shows the mean of total scores and scale scores of the emotional intelligence. Table 2 explains the effects of personal and social variables in the managers and employees' emotional intelligence scores. This table shows that there is no significant difference between emotional intelligence of female and male managers and

employees ($p = 0.33$) and manager and employee ($p = 0.78$). Further evaluation also showed no significant difference among managers and employees' emotional intelligence categories with communication effectiveness.

However, further evaluations showed a significant difference between the self-regard and motivation ($p = 0.004$). Also, there was a significant difference between managers and employees' emotional intelligence in all categories except empathy, responsibility, flexibility, self regard, interpersonal relationship and emotional self-awareness.

TABLE I
MEAN SCORES AND SD OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND ITS SCALES

Category	Mean $\pm$ SD
Happiness	22.96 $\pm$ 4.35
Stress Tolerance	19.34 $\pm$ 4.95
Emotional Self-Awareness	22.23 $\pm$ 3.65
Interpersonal Relationship	23.59 $\pm$ 3.40
Self -Regard	22.95 $\pm$ 3.50
Flexibility	19.43 $\pm$ 3.81
Empathy	24.79 $\pm$ 3.07
Problem Solving	23.15 $\pm$ 3.18
Independence	21.97 $\pm$ 3.17
Self-Actualization	23.08 $\pm$ 3.37
Reality Testing	20.16 $\pm$ 3.96
Optimism	22.91 $\pm$ 3.94
Impulse Control	19.22 $\pm$ 5.24
Responsibility	25.76 $\pm$ 2.66
Assertiveness	20.47 $\pm$ 3.85
Total Score	332.08 $\pm$ 39.80

TABLE II
COMPARISON BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF MANAGERS AND EMPLOYEES IN EDUCATIONAL ADMINISTRATIONS OF IRAN BASED ON THEIR DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

Variables	Groups	Mean and SD	Scales
Sex	Male	337.50 $\pm$ 33.62	t = 0.97, df = 142
	Female	330.14 $\pm$ 41.77	P = 0.33
Individual Type	Manager	333.27 $\pm$ 42.62	t = 0.28, df = 142
	Employee	331.36 $\pm$ 38.24	P = 0.78

The emotional intelligence of managers and employees in educational administrations of Iran was compared by ANOVA, which showed no significant difference between them ($f = 1.31$, $p = 0.26$). Also, ANOVA showed no significant difference among the emotional intelligence of managers and employees in different birth ranks ($f = 1.59$, $p = 0.20$). Moreover, the Pearson correlation coefficient showed no significant relation between age and emotional intelligence ($r = -0.06$, $p = 0.45$).

XIV. CONCLUSION

Managers should have a positive self-regard in order to be self motivated and have a stable self, to be motivated to learn and communicate effectively with employees. When managers

have high regards for themselves, they will be high achievers academically and good citizen. It is very important for managers to be stable and have all the positive traits because they are the ones who are going to decide the country's harmony and prosperity. Everybody should play a key role in increasing positive self regard and encourage motivation to learn among employees and developing the effectively communication in organizations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank University Technology Malaysia (UTM) for its invaluable help in developing and setting up the social tag infrastructure, and in post-processing the raw data. The authors are grateful for the organizations and support they received from Educational Administrations of Iran.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abraham, R. (1999). Emotional intelligence in organizations :A conceptualization. *Genetic, Social, and General Psychology Monographs*, 125 :209-224.
- [2] Asimov, I. (1987). *Beginnings :The story of origins -of mankind, life, the earth, the universe*. New York :Berkley Books.
- [3] Barbuto, J.E. Jr., & Burbach, M.E. (2006). The emotional intelligence of transformational leaders :A field study of elected officials. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 146, 51-64.
- [4] Barling, J., Slater, F., & Kelloway, K. (2000). Transformational leadership and emotional intelligence :An exploratory study. *Leadership and Organizational Development Journal*, 21:157-161.
- [5] Bar-On R. (2006). The Bar-On Model of Emotional-Social Intelligence (ESI). *Psicothema*; 18 Suppl :13-25.
- [6] Chen, L. (1996). Cognitive complexity, situational influence, and topic selection in intercultural and intercultural dyadic interactions. *Communication Reports*, 9(1), 1-12.
- [7] Dijk, C., & Freedman, J. (2007). Differentiating emotional intelligence in leadership. *Journal of Leadership Studies*, 1(2), 8-20.
- [8] Edmondson, A., Roberto, M. A., & Watkins, M. (2003). A dynamic model of top management team effectiveness :Managing unstructured task streams. *Leadership Quarterly*, 14(3), 297-325.
- [9] Ferres, N., & Travaglione, T. & O'Neill, G. (2005). Role of emotional intelligence within transactional-transformational leadership. *Journal of Business and Leadership :Research, Practice, and Teaching*, 1:68-79.
- [10] Fisher, H. (1999). *The first sex :The natural talents of women and how they are changing the world*. New York :Ballantine Books.
- [11] Gardner, L. & Stough, C. (2002). Examining the relationship between leadership and emotional intelligence in senior level managers. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 23:68-78.
- [12] Goleman, D. (1995). *Emotional intelligence :Why it can matter more than IQ for character, health and lifelong achievement*. New York, NY :Bantman press.
- [13] Goleman, D. (1998). *Working with emotional intelligence*. New York, NY :Bantman press.
- [14] Goleman, D. (1998b). What makes a leader? *Harvard Business Review*, November -December.
- [15] Gudykunst, W. B. (2005). An anxiety/uncertainty management (AUM) theory of effective communication :Making the mesh of the net finer. In W. B. Gudykunst (Ed.), *Theorizing about intercultural communication* (pp. 281 -322). Thousand Oaks, CA :Sage.
- [16] Hackman, M. Z., & Johnson, C. E. (1991). *Leadership :A Communication Perspective*. Prospect Heights, Ill :Waveland press.
- [17] Helgeson, S. (1990). *The female advantage :Women's ways of leadership*. New York: Doubleday.
- [18] Hersey, P., Blanchard, K., & Johnson, D. (2001). *Management of organizational behavior :Leading human resources* (8th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ :Prentice Hall.
- [19] Luftman, J. N. (2004). *Managing the information technology resource : Leadership in the information age*. Upper Saddle River, NJ :Pearson Education Inc.

- [20] Marshak, R. (2004). Generative conversations :How to use deep listening and transforming talk n coaching and consulting .*OD Practitioner*, 3, 25-29.
- [21] Matthews, G., Zeinder, M., & Roberts, R.D (2002). *Emotional Intelligence :Science and myth*. Cambridge, MA :A Bradford Book.
- [22] Mayer, J.D., & Salovey, P. (1997). What is emotional intelligence? In P. Salovey & D. Sluyter (Eds.), *Emotional development and emotional intelligence :Educational implications* (pp.3-31). New York :Basic Books.
- [23] Palmer, B., Walls, M., Burgess, Z., & Stough, C. (2001). Emotional intelligence and effective leadership. *Leadership and Organizational Development Journal*, 22:1-7.
- [24] Rosete, D. & Ciarrochi, J. (2005). Emotional intelligence and its relationship to workplace performance. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 26(5), 388-399.
- [25] Schermerhorn, J. R., Hunt, J. G. & Osborn, R. N. (2003). *Organizational behavior (8th ed.)*. New York :Wiley and Sons, Inc.
- [26] Sosik, J. J., & Megerian, L. E. (1999). Understanding leader emotional intelligence and performance :The role of self-other agreement on transformational leadership perceptions .*Group & Organization Management*, 24 :367-390.
- [27] Thamhain, H. (1992). *Engineering management :Managing effectively in technology-based organizations*. New York :John Wiley & Sons.
- [28] *Webster's Dictionary* (2001). Allied Publishing Group, Inc.
- [29] Wood, J. (2003). *Gendered lives :Communication, gender, and culture*. Belmont, CA :Thomson Wadsworth.
- [30] Woolfolk, A.E. (1993). *Educational Psychology*. Boston :Allyn & Bacon
- [31] Anthony, R.N., Govindarajan, V., (1998). *Management Control Systems*. Richard D. Irwin.
- [32] Scott, D. (2008). Effective VoIP Learning Experiences: The Relationship between Adult Learners' Motivation, Multiple Intelligences, and Learning Styles *International Journal of Learning* 15(3), 63-78.
- [33] Lanser, E.G. (2000). Why you should care about your emotional intelligence. *Healthcare Executive*, (Nov/Dec), 6-11.
- [34] Dong, Q., Aden, T., Araisa, S., Armagnac, W., Cartwright, P., Domingo, B., Kemper, M., and LaMay, B. The Impact of Self Esteem and Media Information Seeking on Emotional Intelligence (May, 2005). The paper presented at the International Communication Association Conference, New York City, New York.
- [35] Dulewicz, V., & Higgs, M. J. (2003). Design of a new instrument to assess leadership dimensions and styles. *Henley Working Paper Series* HWP 0311. Henley-on-Thames, UK: Henley Management College.
- [36] Langley, A. (2000) 'Emotional intelligence—a new evaluation for management development?', *Career Development International*, vol. 5, no. 3
- [37] Cherniss, C., & Goleman, D. (1998). Bringing emotional intelligence to the workplace [On-line]. Available at: http://www.eiconsortium.org/technical_report.htm (technical report). Piscataway, NJ: Rutgers University, The Consortium for Research on Emotional Intelligence in Organizations.
- [38] Dries, N., & Pepermans, R. (2008). "Real" high-potential careers: An empirical study into the perspectives of organisations and high potentials. *Personnel Review*, 37(1), 85 - 108.
- [39] Diggins, C., „EI: The key to effective performance”, *Human Resource Management International Digest*, 12(1), 2004, pp. 33-35.
- [40] Kernis, M. H., & Paradise, A. W. (2002). Distinguishing between fragile and secure forms of high self-esteem. In E. L. Deci & R. M. Ryan (Eds.), *Selfdetermination: Theoretical issues and practical applications*. Rochester, NY: University of Rochester Press.
- [41] Sternberg, R. & Vroom, V. (2002). The person versus the situation in leadership. *Leadership Quarterly*, 13, pp. 301-323.
- [42] Kernis, M.H., Paradise, A.W., Whitaker, D., Wheatman, S., & Goldman, B. (2000). Master of one's psychological domain? Not likely if one's self-esteem is unstable. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 26, 1297-1305.
- [43] Gecas, V. (1982). The self-concept. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 8, 1-33.
- [44] Gecas, V. & Schwalbe, M.L. (1983). Beyond the looking-glass self: Social structure and self-efficacy based self-esteem. *Social Psychology Quarterly* 46(2), 77-88.
- [45] Rosenberg, M., Schooler, C., Schoenbach, C., & Rosenberg, F. (1990, February). Global self-esteem and specific self-esteem: different concepts, different outcomes. *American Sociological Review*, 60(1), 141-157.
- [46] Swann, W. B., Jr., Hixon, J. G., Stein-Seroussi, A., & Gilbert, D. T. (1990). The fleeting gleam of praise: Cognitive processes underlying behavioral reactions to self-relevant feedback. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 59, 17-26.
- [47] Caldwell, R. M., Silverman, J., Lefforge, N., & Silver, N. C. (2004). Familial emotional support, self-esteem, and emotional well-being as predictors of delinquency among adjudicated Mexican American adolescents. *The American Journal of Family Therapy*, 32, 55-69.
- [48] Patterson, C. J., Cohn, D. A., & Kao, B. T. (1989). Maternal warmth as a protective factor against risks associated with peer rejection among children. *Development and Psychopathology*, 1, 21-38.
- [49] Snyder, J., & Patterson, G. (1987). Family interaction and delinquent behavior. In H. C. Quay (Ed.), *Handbook of Juvenile Delinquency*. New York: Wiley.
- [50] Greenier, K. D., Kernis, M. H., McNamara, C. W., Waschull, S. B., Berry, A. J., Herlocker, C. E., & Abend, T. A. (1999). Individual differences in reactivity to daily events: examining the roles of stability and level of self-esteem. *Journal of Personality*, 67, 185-208.
- [51] Kuncoro, Mudrajad. (2007). *Ekonomi Industri Indonesia 2030*. Yogyakarta: ANDI.
- [52] Qureshi, S., Liu, M. and Vogel, D. (2005) A grounded theory analysis of e-collaboration effects for distributed project management, in R. Sprague and J. Nunamaker (eds) *Proceedings of the Thirty Eight Annual Hawaii International Conference on Systems Sciences*, January 3-6, 2005, Waikoloa, Island of Hawaii, USA, IEEE Computer Society Press, 1- 10.
- [53] H. R. Arkes and J. P. Garske, *Psychological theories of motivation*, 2nd ed., 1982, ch. Optimal Level Theories, pp. 172–195.
- [54] Johnson, R., Johnson, D.W., & Stanne, M. (1985). Effects of cooperative, competitive, and individualistic goal structures on computer-assisted instruction. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 77, 668–677.
- [55] Gibson, C. B., & Gibbs, J. L. 2006. Unpacking the concept of virtuality: The effects of geographic dispersion, electronic dependence, dynamic structure, and national diversity on team innovation. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 51(3): 451-495.